

The Factors Affecting Staffs at Primary Health Centre Nuni Pantai Utara District Sub Province Manokwari Papua Barat Province

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ABSTRACT

Background: Employee performance is very important in achieving organizational goals to achieve vision and mission. Nuni Health Center as a health service facility requires employee performance that is influenced by age, work motivation, incentives, workload, facilities and infrastructure, abilities and skills, work discipline and leadership.

The purpose of the study: to find out the factors that influences the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency

Research Method: Analytical with cross sectional study design. The population is employees at the Nuni Health Center and a sample of 33 people with total sampling. Data were obtained using a questionnaire and analyzed using the chi square test and logistic binary regression.

Research results: Factors that influence the performance of employees in Nuni Health Center, Manokwari Regency are work motivation (p-value = 0.005; RP = 3.938; CI95% = (1,538 - 10,083), incentives (p-value = 0,003; RP = 5,844; CI95 % = (1,525 - 22,387), workload (p-value = 0,003; RP = 0,171; CI95% = (0,045 - 0,656), facilities (p-value = 0,009; RP = 3,200; CI95% = (1,366 - 7,496) , skill ability (p-value = 0.001; RP = 4,500; CI95% = (1,777 - 11,390), work discipline (p-value = 0,004; RP = 4,524; CI95% = (1,521 - 13,455) and leadership of the head of the puskesmas (p -value = 0.023; RP = 3.542; CI95% = (1,185 - 10,585). Factors that do not affect the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency are age (p-value = 0.296; Rp = 0.588; CI95% = (0.243 - 1,425) The dominant factor that influences the performance of employees at Puskesmas Nuni, Manokwari Regency is the workload and leadership.

Keyword: Performance, Staff, Health Primary Centre

1. INTRODUCTION

Professional employees can be interpreted as a view to always think, work hard, work full time, discipline, honest, high loyalty, and full of dedication for the success of their work. Performance is someone's success in carrying out tasks, work results that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authority

and responsibility or about how someone is expected to function and behave in accordance with the tasks assigned to him and quantity, quality and the time used in carrying out tasks (Sutrisno, 2010).

Get optimal work results, one of which is the ability of leaders in directing employees to be willing do what the company wants. Leader in an organization, both profit oriented and non-profit oriented

positions dominant in determining the back and forth of a company.

That performance produced by a company is a description of the ownership of results given by the leader managing the company (Fahmi, 2013).

A leader must develop an attitude in leading his subordinates. A leadership attitude can be formulated as a behavior pattern that is formed to be aligned with the interests of the organization and employees to be able to achieve the stated goals (Nasution (1994) in Riyadi, 2011). The role of the Head of Puskesmas is very important to move his subordinates to become a good work team through motivation, so that motivation can improve the performance of his subordinates such as being on time, care provided in accordance with procedures and documenting the patient's health development.

This opinion reflects how big the leadership role in an organization, so that a leader is expected to have reliable leadership skills so that organizational goals can be achieved. As for what is meant by the ability of a leader is the ability to motivate, influence, direct and communicate with subordinates. Besides that leaders must also have behaviors or ways of leadership that are adapted to the situation and conditions of the organization, which is flexible, meaning being able to adapt or adapt to the subordinate's environment (Herlambang, 2012). Some health workers at Nuni Health Center showed low work discipline seen from absenteeism, employees who arrived late, from observations and information obtained from the head of the staffing department, it was found that the enthusiasm for carrying out activities was still low, and this indicated the low performance of some employees towards puskesmas . In this case the researcher wants to present seven factors, namely motivation factors, incentives, workload, facilities and infrastructure, abilities and skills and work discipline and leadership of the Head of Nuni Health Center. This selection is based on the fact

that the eight factors appear most often in theories that discuss factors that influence employee performance. Work discipline is a form of obedience from a person's behavior in complying with certain provisions or regulations relating to work, and is applied in an organization. the average attendance rate is 85% of attendance every month on weekdays.

Based on the description of the problem above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title "Factors that Affect Employee Performance in Nuni Health Center North Coast District, Manokwari Regency, West Papua Province"

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Type of Research

This study is an analytical study with a cross sectional study design that aims to determine the effect of two or more variables (Sugiyono, 2013). This study explains the relationship affects and is influenced by the variables to be studied. Using a quantitative approach because the data will be used to analyze the relationships between variables expressed by numbers or numerical scales (Sastroasmoro, 2010).

B. Time and Location of Research

This research was carried out at the Nuni Health Center in September 2018.

C. Population and sample

1. Population

The populations in this study were 33 employees at the Nuni Health Center.

2. Samples

The sample is part of the generalization of the population studied (Sugiyono, 2013). If the population is less than 100, then the sample size is the total population. The sampling technique uses a saturated sampling technique. Thus the sample size was 33 people as a sample in total sampling because the Head of the Puskesmas was not included as a respondent in the study.

3. RESULTS

Bivariate Analysis

a. Effect of age on employee performance

Based on Table 1, it shows that out of 17 employees aged <30 years as many as 5 people (20.4%) have less performance and as many as 12 people (70.6%) in the good category. Of the 16 employees > 30 years of age, 8 people (50%) had less performance and as many as 8 people (50%). The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.296 > 0.05. This means that there is no influence of age on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency Test results of the prevalence ratio Rp. 0.588; CI95% = (0.243 - 1.425) in the number 1 interpreted by age is not a risk factor for employee performance.

Table 1. Effect of age on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Age	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	≤ 30 year	5	20,4	12	70,6	17	100
2	> 30 year	8	50	8	50	16	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,296; RP = 0,588; CI95%= (0,243 - 1,425)

b. Effect of work motivation on employee performance

Table 2. Effect of motivation on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Motivation	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Low	9	75	3	25	12	100
2	High	4	19	17	81	21	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,005; RP = 3,938; CI95%= (1,538 - 10,083)

Based on Table 2, shows that out of 12 employees whose work motivation is low as many as 9 people (75%) have less performance and as many as 3 people (25%) good performance. Of the 21 employees who have high work motivation, 4 people (19%) have less performance and as many as 17 people (81%). The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.005 < 0.05. This means that there is an influence of work motivation on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 3,938; CI95% = (1,538 - 10,083) which is

interpreted that employees who have low work motivation tend to perform less than 3,938 times higher than employees who have high work motivation.

c. Effect of incentives on employee performance

Table 3. Effect of Incentives on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Incentive	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	11	68,8	5	31,3	16	100
2	Enough	2	11,8	15	88,2	17	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,003; RP = 5,844; CI95%= (1,525 - 22,387)

Based on Table 3, shows that of the 16 employees who stated that there were less incentives as many as 11 people (68.8%) had less performance and as many as 5 people (31.3%) had good performance. Of the 17 employees who have enough incentives as many as 2 people (11.8%) have less performance and as many as 15 people (88.2%) have good performance. The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.003 < 0.05. This means that there is an effect of incentives on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 5,844; CI95% = (1,525 - 22,387) interpreted that employees who get incentives are less likely to have less performance as much as 5,844 times higher than employees who get sufficient incentives.

d. Effect of workload on employee performance

Table 4. Effect of workload on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Workload	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	High	2	11,8	15	88,2	17	100
2	Low	11	68,8	5	31,3	16	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,003; RP = 0,171; CI95%= (0,045 - 0,656)

Based on Table 4, it shows that out of 17 employees with a high workload of 2 people (11.8%) have less performance and as many as 15 people (88.2%) have good performance. Of the 16 employees who had a low workload of 11 people (68.8%) had less performance and as many as 5 people

(31.3%) had good performance. The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.003 <0.05. This means that there is an influence of workload on the performance of employees in the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency When viewed from the RP value = 0.171; CI95% = (0.045 - 0.656) in number 1 interpreted that workload is not a risk factor for the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency.

e. Effect of infrastructure on employee performance

Table 5. Effect of infrastructure on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Infrastructure	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	8	72,7	3	27,3	11	100
2	Enough	5	22,7	17	77,3	22	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,009; RP = 3,200; CI95%= (1,366 – 7,496)

Based on Table 5, it shows that of the 11 employees who stated that the infrastructure was inadequate with less than 89 people (72.7%) and as many as 3 people (27.3%) had good employees. Of the 22 employees who stated good infrastructure as many as 5 people (22.7%) had less performance and as many as 17 people (77.3%) had good performance. The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.009 <0.05. This means that there is an influence of infrastructure on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 3,200; CI95% = (1,366 - 7,496) interpreted that employees with infrastructure facilities who lack work performance are 3,200 times compared to employees who state that infrastructure facilities are sufficient.

f. Effect of skills ability on employee performance

Table 6. Effect of skills ability on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	skills ability	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	9	81,8	2	18,2	11	100
2	Good	4	18,2	18	81,8	22	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,001; RP = 4,500; CI95%= (1,777 – 11,390)

Based on Table 6, it shows that out of 11 employees the ability of work skills is less than 9 people (81.8%) have less performance and as many as 2 people (18.2%) have good performance. Of the 22 employees who have good work skills, 4 people (18.2%) have poor performance and as many as 18 people (81.8%) have good performance. The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.001 <0.05. This means that there is an influence on the ability of skills to the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. When viewed from a value of Rp = 4,500; CI95% = (1,777 - 11,390) which is interpreted that employees who have less skill abilities tend to have a performance that is less than 4,500 times higher than employees who have good job skills.

g. Effect of work discipline on employee performance

Table 7. The effect of work discipline on employee performance at Nuni Health Center

No	Work discipline	Performance				Number	
		Less		Good		n	%
		n	%	n	%		
1	Less	10	71,4	4	28,6	14	100
2	Good	3	15,8	16	84,2	19	100
Total		13	39,4	20	60,6	33	100

p-value = 0,004; RP = 4,524; CI95%= (1,521 – 13,455)

Based on Table 7, it shows that of the 14 employees lacking work discipline as many as 10 people (71.4%) have less performance and as many as 4 people (28.6%) have good performance. Of the 19 employees who had good work discipline as many as 3 people (15.8%) had less performance and as many as 16 people (84.2%) had good performance. The results of the chi square test obtained p-value = 0.004 <0.05. This means that there is an influence of work discipline on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. When viewed from the value of RP = 4,524; CI95% = (1,521 - 13,455) which is interpreted that employees who have a work discipline are less likely to have a performance that is less than 4,524 times higher than employees who have good work discipline at work.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Effect of age on employee performance

The results showed that there was no effect of age on employee performance in the Nuni Health Center (p -value = 0.296). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Barata (2013) in Puskesmas in Gianyar Regency that age does not have a significant relationship with the performance of officers. The age factor can affect one's physical and psychological strength and at a certain age an employee will experience changes in work potential. Senior employees tend to be satisfied with their work because they are better able to adapt to the environment based on their experience. They tend to be more emotionally stable, so that overall they can work more smoothly and regularly

Age is the span of life span from birth and age (Handayani, 2010). Age will affect a person's physical condition, enthusiasm, burden and responsibility both in work and in daily life. For employees who are less than 30 years old, even though they have good physical condition, to carry out physical activities but in general they have a relatively less sense of responsibility compared to those aged > 30 years (Sandra, 2013).

The results of the analysis showed that 20.4% of employees aged <30 years had less performance and 50% of employees who worked > 30 years had less performance. Test results of the prevalence ratio Rp. 0.588; CI95% = (0.243 - 1,425) below number 1 which is interpreted as age is not a risk factor for employee performance. The absence of influence can be caused by other factors that affect employee performance not due to physical age of the employee, but the environment in the health center such as the existence of rewards, so employees do not feel satisfied in work that affects employee performance. Judging from the age limit of employees aged > 30 years the oldest is 51 years old and the youngest is 22 years old, so that physically does not affect the performance

of employees who are still in their productive age. The average employee aged <30 years is an employee with an employee honor status or contract, so employees will compete - to create good performance so that they can be considered and become a priority in the reception of civil servants. The same thing is done by employees aged > 30 years, most of whom are civil servants and have an influence on satisfaction and motivation for career divisions that are good and equal - at the same risk of having good performance, so as not to affect performance.

This is in accordance with the theory proposed by Gibson (2003), that age has an indirect effect on individual behavior and performance. The older a person is, not necessarily able to show intellectual maturity both cognitively and psychomotor when doing work. This is probably due to the personal values of the individual concerned, flexibility and other psychological factors that influence.

4.2. Effect of motivation on employee performance

The results showed that there was a significant effect of motivation on employee performance in the Nuni Health Center (p -value = 0.005). The low work motivation tends to be less than 3,938 times higher than employees who have high work motivation. Employees whose work motivation is low as much as 75% have less performance and employees who have high work motivation as much as 19% have less performance and as many as 17 people (81%).

The results of this study are in line with Baratha's (2013) research in Gianyar District Health Center that there is an effect of motivation on employee performance. Motivation is an act of a group of factors that cause individuals to behave in certain ways (Herlambang, 2012). Motivation teaches how to encourage subordinate work morale so that they want to work harder and work hard by using all their abilities and skills to be able to advance and achieve company goals. While the motivation is the driving force that results in an organization

member willing and willing to time to organize various activities into his responsibility and fulfill his obligations in the number of achievement of goals and various organizational goals that have been determined previously (Siagian, 2010).

Statement of respondents about motivation in working with low motivation that each work or provide services to patients must require colleagues. This causes employee independence to decrease. In other words, employees have a high morale when they share - with other employees. In addition, employees do not feel proud of the results of services that get appreciation from leaders or coworkers. This shows that employee motivation seems to have other needs that must be considered by the health center management.

Employees who have high motivation are caused by always trying various alternatives to achieve success, good cooperation among friends encourages to work hard so that it can complete good work, make plans to achieve success, if you have difficulty doing something, you prefer to try hard to finish it, feel satisfied when you get the best results and if it works well. In addition, employees are confident in my ability to work well and provide services to patients quickly and try to be responsible for the work seriously to prepare themselves to face the challenges of work and get a promotion. This shows that employees have the motivation to actualize. Self-actualization is related to the process of developing one's true potential. The need to show the ability, expertise and potential of someone. Self-actualization needs have a potential tendency that increases because people actualize their behavior. A person who is dominated by the need for self-actualization likes tasks that challenge his abilities and expertise (Sofyandi and Garniwa, 2007).

The prevalence ratio test results obtained that employees who have a low risk of motivation have less performance 1.709 times higher than employees who are highly motivated. The influence of

motivation on employee performance is caused by employees doing their jobs well due to the expectation that they can fulfill their needs through promotion, so that they compete or compete in obtaining a promotion which influences the incentives or compensation they receive.

4.3. The effect of incentives on employee performance

Wage incentives are intended to provide different wages because of different work performance. Implementation of this incentive model to increase employee productivity (Nawawi, 2007). The basic purpose of this incentive wage is to motivate good achievement by linking achievement and reward (Dessler, 2011).

The results of the study showed that there was an effect of incentives on employee performance at Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency. Employees who declare less incentives as much as 68.8% have less performance and employees whose incentives work enough as many as 11.8% have less performance. This shows that the less insignificant given, the less employee performance. This is strong from the results of the prevalence ratio test interpreted that employees who get incentives are less likely to have less performance as much as 5,844 times higher than employees who get sufficient incentives.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Darmawan (2008) about the incentive for nurses in RSUDDr. H. Soewondo stated that there was no relationship between giving incentives to performance. The influence of incentives on employee performance is due to the fact that the provision of incentives has been regulated in accordance with Permenkes No. 21 of 2016 concerning the provision of incentives for workers or health workers at the Puskesmas. The existence of regulations or arrangements that have been determined by the ministry of health is sufficient and fair to provide incentives for employees. However, for employees who are diligent in their work and have a good

working spirit compared to their other colleagues and giving incentives that are equally large, they will feel the immediate impact of dissatisfaction at work, because what they do is treated unfairly and reduces employee morale. 2. Effect of workload on employee performance. Every work done will be a physical and mental burden. A workforce has different abilities in relation to workload. Human activity can be classified into physical work (muscle) and mental work (brain). Even though it cannot be separated, work can still be distinguished from physical domination and work with a dominance of mental activities (Mutia, 2014).

The results showed that there was a significant effect between the workload on the performance of the Manokwari District Health Office staff and from the results of the prevalence ratio test interpreted that the workload was not a risk factor for the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency. Employees who stated that a high workload of 11.8% had less performance and employees who had good work discipline as many as 11 people (68.8%) had less performance and as many as 5 people (31.3%) had good performance. The distribution of respondents' responses shows that high workloads can influence employees' psychology and psychology. Previous research by Ayer (2016) in the Syiori District Agricultural Service revealed that there was an effect of workload on employee performance. According to Hasibuan (2012) that human resources are integrated capabilities of the mind and physical power possessed by individuals. Behavior and physical are determined by heredity and environment. While work performance is motivated by the desire to fulfill the desire for satisfaction.

Employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency also mentioned the decline in performance due to the high workload and the lack of appreciation given for the performance achieved by employees. The above

conditions cause internal problems achievement of the performance of the Manokwari District Health Office. The response of employees who stated a high workload because a lot of work every day that must be immediately resolved which is not in accordance with the standard of work or ability to cause employees not to enjoy the work done.

There needs to be attention from the management in giving assignments and work that is evenly distributed to each employee, so that the workload is felt the same. In addition, employees with high workloads must be adjusted to the appropriate incentives.

4.4. Effect of Facilities and Infrastructure on employee performance

The results of the study showed that there was an effect of infrastructure on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency. Employees who stated that infrastructure facilities were inadequate with a lack of performance of 2.7% and employees who declared good infrastructure as much as 22.7%. This shows that the lack of infrastructure affects the performance process by employees. The research conducted by Putranti (2013), that there is an influence of the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure that support the performance of officers in work. Moenir (2012) argues that facilities are all types of equipment, work equipment and facilities that function as the main or auxiliary tools in carrying out work and also in the framework of interests that are currently associated with work organizations. The definition clearly gives the direction that the suggestion and infrastructure is a set of tools used in a process of activities both the tools are auxiliary equipment and the main equipment, both of which function to realize the goals to be achieved

Inadequate facilities and infrastructure for work facilities that are not evenly distributed across all employees cannot maximize the effectiveness of task implementation and the availability of

adequate facilities and infrastructure cannot support the completion of work in a relatively short time. Geographical conditions as well as inadequate facilities and infrastructure such as electricity, transportation with long distances with difficult terrain and physical equipment such as computers and printing equipment cause delayed reporting of accountability reported every month at the Manokwari District Health Office. This is evident from the prevalence ratio value that inadequate facilities and infrastructure have the opportunity to have a performance that is less than 3,200 times greater than adequate facilities and infrastructure. This is in accordance with the theory raised by Gibson in Ilyas (2001) that the availability of facilities and infrastructure affect the performance of individuals.

4.5. Effect of ability and skills on employee performance

Ability and skills are the main factors that influence individual behavior and performance (Gibson, 2003). The results showed that employees who had the ability to lack work skills as much as 81.8% had poor performance and employees who had good job skills ability 18.2% had less performance. The results of the chi square test obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.001 < 0.05$, which means that there is an influence on the ability of skills to the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center. Test results of $R_p = 4,500$; $CI_{95\%} = (1,777 - 11,390)$ which is interpreted that employees who have less skills are less likely to have a performance that is less than 4,500 times higher than employees who have good job skills.

The research conducted by Sanjaya (2018) revealed that the ability of employees to influence employee performance. Hasibuan (2012) says that work performance is a person's ability in an effort to achieve better / more prominent work towards the achievement of organizational goals. According to Mangkunegara (2015) defining performance or work performance is as a result of the

work of people in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him in a specified period of time. Human resources are one of the factors that become the main capital in an organization and have a complex soul / very complicated to understand. Therefore, human resources need to be managed professionally in order to realize a balance between the needs of employees and the demands and capabilities of the organization.

The lack of ability of employees at the Manokwari District Health Office from employee responses is due to the lack of education and knowledge in the field of work, being unable to work quickly in completing routine tasks, being easy and careful and not feeling comfortable with working environment conditions. The ability of employees who are not in accordance with their scientific discipline causes regret of the task to be hampered while the demands of the work environment are high so that the task is given on time.

Employees who have good abilities at the Manokwari District Health Office are able to adapt well to the level of difficulty of the work they do and are ready to accept work challenges. The ability of an employee is very useful to help organizations create a high work culture. Pleru's attention from the Manokwari District Health Office in the framework of forming qualified personnel is one of the dominant elements that is supported by education and training in accordance with its field plan so that it can run smoothly, due to the development of human resources as a development resource, emphasizing human as development actors who have a work ethic that is productive, skilled, creative, disciplined, professional and capable of utilizing, developing and mastering existing knowledge and technology and management capabilities

4.6 Effect of work discipline on employee performance

Hasibuan (2012) argues that discipline is the awareness and willingness

of someone to comply with all applicable company regulations and social norms. Based on the above understanding it can be concluded that work discipline is an attitude, behavior, and action that is in accordance with both written and unwritten rules, and if it violates there will be sanctions for violations. The results showed that employees who lacked work discipline 71.4% had less performance employees who had good work discipline as much as 15.8% had less performance. The results of the chi square test were obtained which stated that there was an influence of work discipline on the performance of employees in the Nuni Health Center and from the test results from the value of $RP = 4,524$; $CI95\% = (1,521 - 13,455)$ which is interpreted that employees who have a work discipline are less likely to have a performance that is less than 4,524 times higher than employees who have good work discipline at work.

The results of this study are in line with Salam's (2013) research at the Wara Selatan Health Center in Palopo City, which revealed that the influence of work discipline on employee performance. The respondent's statement about discipline is the lowest - the average return from work does not match the predetermined time, does not complete the task in accordance with a predetermined time and does not carry out the boss's orders properly.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. There is no influence of age on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.296$; $Rp = 0.588$; $CI95\% = (0.243 - 1.425)$).
2. There is an influence of work motivation on the performance of employees in Nuni Health Center, Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.005$; $RP = 3.938$; $CI95\% = (1.538 - 10.083)$).
3. There is an effect of incentives on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency

($p\text{-value} = 0.003$; $RP = 5.844$; $CI95\% = (1,525 - 22,387)$).

4. There is an effect of workload on employee performance in Nuni Health Center, Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.003$; $RP = 0.171$; $CI95\% = (0.045 - 0.656)$).
5. There is the influence of facilities on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.009$; $RP = 3.200$; $CI95\% = (1,366 - 7,496)$).
5. There is an influence of skills ability on employee performance in Nuni Health Center, Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.001$; $RP = 4,500$; $CI95\% = (1,777 - 11,390)$).
6. There is the influence of work discipline on the performance of employees at the Nuni Health Center in Manokwari Regency ($p\text{-value} = 0.004$; $RP = 4,524$; $CI95\% = (1,521 - 13,455)$).

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